

JAVASCRIPT-DA OB'EKTLARNI YARATISH VA ULARGA KIRISH

Yuldoshev Inomjon Nizomjon o'g'li

Qo'qon davlat pedagogika instituti

Fizika – matematika fakulteti

301 – MI guruh talabasi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7924961>

Anotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda ob'ektlarni qanday yaratish, ob'ektlarning xossalari va usullarini qo'shish va o'zgartirish, shuningdek ularga qanday kirish mumkinligi muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zi: JavaScript, ob'ektlar.

Аннотация: В этой тезис обсуждается, как создавать объекты, добавлять и изменять свойства и методы объекта, а также как получить к ним доступ.

Ключевые слова: JavaScript, объекты.

Abstract: This thesis discusses how to create objects, add and modify object properties and methods, and how to access them.

Keywords: JavaScript, objects.

JavaScript - bu interaktiv veb-sahifalarni yaratish uchun tez-tez ishlatiladigan dasturlash tili. JavaScript -dagi hamma narsa ob'ekt, jumladan raqamlar va satrlar kabi ibtidoiy ma'lumotlar turlari. Ob'ektlar - bu funktsiyalar yoki boshqa ob'ektlar bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan xususiyatlar to'plami. JavaScript -da ob'ekt yaratish jingalak qavslar {} ichiga olingan va vergul bilan ajratilgan xususiyatlar va ularning qiymatlari ro'yxatini o'z ichiga olgan literal ob'ekt yordamida amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Masalan :

```
let myObj = {  
  name: "John",  
  age: 30,  
  city: "New York"  
};
```

Ob'ektning xususiyatlariga nuqta belgilari yoki kvadrat qavslar yordamida kirish mumkin. Masalan :

```
let myName = myObj.name; // получить значение свойства name объекта myObj  
let myAge = myObj["age"]; // получить значение свойства age объекта myObj
```

Bundan tashqari, konstruktor funksiyasi yoki klassi yordamida ob'ektlarni yaratishingiz mumkin, bu sizga bir xil xususiyat va usullarga ega bo'lgan bir nechta ob'ekt namunalarni yaratishga imkon beradi.

Masalan, konstruktor funksiyasi quyidagicha ko'rinishi mumkin:

```
function Person(name, age, city) {  
  this.name = name;  
  this.age = age;  
  this.city = city;  
}
```

```
let person1 = new Person("John", 30, "New York"); // создать новый экземпляр объекта Person
```

```
let person2 = new Person("Jane", 25, "Los Angeles"); // создать новый экземпляр объекта Person
```

nomi , yoshi va shahar xususiyatlari uchun o'z qiymatlariga ega .

JavaScript- da ob'ektlarni qanday yaratish va ularga kirishning kichik bir ko'rinishi .
 Qo'shimcha savollaringiz bo'lsa, iltimos, bemalol so'rang!

JavaScript -dagi ob'ektlar o'zgaruvchan bo'lishi mumkin, ya'ni ular yaratilgandan keyin ularning xususiyatlari va usullarini o'zgartirishingiz mumkin. Masalan :

```
let myObj = {
  name: "John",
  age: 30,
  city: "New York"
};
```

```
myObj.age = 31; // изменить значение свойства age объекта myObj
```

Bundan tashqari, istalgan vaqtda ob'ektga faqat nomi bilan murojaat qilish va yangi xususiyat yoki usulni ko'rsatish orqali ob'ektlarga yangi xususiyatlar va usullarni qo'shishingiz mumkin.

Masalan :

```
let myObj = {
  name: "John",
  age: 30,
  city: "New York"
};
```

```
myObj.gender = "male"; // добавить новое свойство gender объекта myObj
```

```
myObj.sayHello = function() {
```

```
  console.log("Hello!");
```

```
}; // добавить новый метод sayHello объекта myObj
```

Bundan tashqari, ob'ektlar ichki joylashtirilishi mumkin, ya'ni siz boshqa ob'ektlarni xususiyat sifatida o'z ichiga olgan ob'ektlarga ega bo'lishingiz mumkin. Masalan :

```
let myObj = {
  name: "John",
  age: 30,
  address: {
    street: "123 Main St",
    city: "New York",
    state: "NY"
  }
};
```

```
let myStreet = myObj.address.street; // получить значение свойства street объекта address в объекте myObj
```

JavaScript- dagi ob'ektlar bilan nima qilishingiz mumkinligining kichik bir qismidir . Ular ma'lumotlarni saqlash va boshqarish, sinflar yaratish va boshqalar uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. Ushbu dasturlash tili bilan muvaffaqiyatli ishlash uchun JavaScript- da ob'ektlarni qanday yaratish va ularga kirishni bilish muhimdir .

Xulosa

Ushbu tezida JavaScript dasturlash tilida ob'ektlarni qanday yaratish, ularning xossalari va usullarini qo'shish va o'zgartirish hamda ularga qanday kirish mumkinligi batafsil yoritilgan. JavaScript-dagi ob'ektlar ma'lumotlarni saqlash va manipulyatsiya qilish, sinflar va boshqa ma'lumotlar tuzilmalarini yaratish uchun muhim vositadir. JavaScript-dagi ob'ektlarni tushunish ushbu dasturlash tili bilan muvaffaqiyatli ishlash uchun juda muhimdir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

- 1."JavaScript dasturlash tilida funksiyalar" avtori Rustamjon Jumayev
- 2.Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Prospects for the development of professional training of students of professional educational institutions using electronic educational resources in the environment of digital transformation." *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research* 3.10 (2022): 158-162.
- 3.Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "The value of open mass competitions in the process of digitalization of extracurricular activities of schoolchildren." *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal* 3.10 (2022): 338-344.
- 4.Jo'rayev, Muzaffarjon. "Professional ta'lim jarayonida fanlararo uzvilik va uzliksizlikni ta'minlash o'quvchilari kasbiy tayyorgarligining muhim omili sifatida." *Zamonaviy dunyoda amaliy fanlar: Muammolar va yechimlar* 1.29 (2022): 43-46.
- 5.Juraev, M. M. "OA Qo'ysinov Description of the methodological basis for ensuring interdisciplinary continuity of the subject "Computer Science and Information Technology" in vocational education." *JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed* 7.10 (2021).
- 6.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Description of the Methodological Basis for Ensuring Interdisciplinary Continuity of the Subject" *Computer Science and Information TECHNOLOGY in Vocational Education.*" *JournalNX* 7.10: 223-225.
- 7.Khasanov, A. R. (2022). LEARNING IS A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH AS A CONTENT UPDATE STEP. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 217-223.
- 8.Khasanov, A. R. (2022). Development of information competence of future informatics teachers as a pedagogical problem. *Open Access Repository*, 9(12), 73-79.
- 9.Xasanov, A. R. (2021, May). USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING COMPUTER SCIENCE. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 198-199).
- 10.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "CURRENT STATUS OF THE SCIENCE OF INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM, EXISTING PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS, PRINCIPLES AND CONTENT OF THE SCIENCE ORGANIZATION." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 10.12 (2022): 327-331.
- 11.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Professional Educational Institutions Theoretical and Practical Basis of Development of the Content of Pedagogical Activity of Teachers of" *Information and Information Technologies.*" *Open Access Repository* 9.12 (2022): 85-89.
- 12.Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Experience Of Cambridge Curricula In Ensuring The Continuity Of Curricula In The Field Of "Computer Science And Information Technology" In The System Of Professional Education." *The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research* 3.11 (2021): 26-32.

13. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Theoretical and practical principles of improving the content of the pedagogical activity of ICT teachers of professional educational institutions in the conditions of information of education." (2022).
14. Juraev, Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich. "Methodological foundations for improving the content of training future ict teachers in the conditions of digital transformation of education." (2022): 9-11.
15. Melikyzievich, Siddikov Ilkhom, et al. "THE METHOD OF REFERENCE TESTS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF DIGITAL DEVICES." International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education 14.7 (2022).
16. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon. "Designing an electronic didactic environment to ensure interdisciplinary integration in the teaching of" Informatics and information technologies" during professional education." Confrencea 11.11 (2023): 78-82.
17. Mansurjonovich, Juraev Muzaffarjon, and Aroyev Dilshod Davronovich. "INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION IS AN IMPORTANT PART OF DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS." Open Access Repository 9.1 (2023): 93-101.
18. Juraev, M. M. "ZY Xudoyberdiyev Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the System of professional education." European Scholar Journal (ESJ)//ISSN (E): 2660-5562.
19. Xudayberdiyev, Zayniddin Yavkachevich, and Muzaffarjon Mansurjonovich Juraev. "Theoretical analysis of the continuity model of computer science and information technology in the system of professional education." (2021).